

Kinetics of Potassium Adsorption and Desorption in some Soils of West Bengal

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To identify the major rate-limiting steps in K adsorption and release in soil, it is imperative that the kinetics of the reactions involved be studied. A number of researchers have investigated kinetic reactions on pure clays and soils¹⁻⁴. Chute and Quirk⁵ revealed that K release from micaceous minerals is diffusion-controlled and the kinetics of exchange conformed to the parabolic diffusion law.

It has been accepted that soils contain sites of differing reactivity for K ions^{6,7}. The rapid kinetics of exchange to external planer sites, slow kinetics of exchange to interlattice exchange sites, and intermediate kinetics of exchange to interlattice-edge sites³ have been studied. The kinetics of K adsorption and desorption in multireactive heterogenous soil systems have successfully employed the first order and the parabolic diffusion law^{3,8}. Application of the parabolic law is based on the assumption that the adsorption process could not be fully explained by either 'film diffusion' or 'intraparticle diffusion'³ theory. The objective of the present study is to evaluate the kinetics of potassium exchange in soil by following the batch technique with a discussion on the usefulness of rate laws in soil systems.

Results and Discussion

The important physicochemical properties of the soil samples studied are presented in Table 1. Table 2 records the kinetics of K adsorption and desorption in the given soils which were found to conform to the first order kinetics (vide Figs. 1 and 2). The values of the corresponding

Fig. 1. First order plots of potassium adsorption in soils.

Fig. 2. First order plots of potassium desorption in soils.

simple linear correlation coefficients (r) for adsorption and desorption ranged from 0.735 to 0.938. Similar observations were made by several workers^{2,3,8}. The adsorption rate coefficient (K_a) of the Mondouri soil was higher (Table 1) than that of other soils. This may possibly be related to the dominance in its clay fraction of smectite and also micaceous minerals which contained a large proportions of interlayer sites⁹. The Mohitnagar soil exhibited a very low K_a value. This was a chlorite-dominated soil, and its exchange sites might be blocked by humic ligands of the organic matter in which this soil was rich. The Bolpur soil contained appreciable amounts of illite, possessing a variety of K-fixing sites. This might have led to a higher K_a in this soil than that in the Anandapur soil which was predominantly kaolinitic in nature (Fig. 3).

The kinetics of K desorption are related to the clay mineralogy of soils¹⁰. The kaolinitic Anandapur soil exhibited a rapid rate of K desorption. This is in agreement with the earlier observations^{11,12}. The slower desorption kinetics in the Bolpur and the Mondouri soils could partly be attributed to the interlayer sites of the 2 : 1 caly minerals that undergo partial collapse upon K adsorption. These results are also in agreement with earlier observation^{13,14}. The Bolpur and Mondouri soils exhibited slower desorption than adsorption, suggesting that potassium reactions were non-

TABLE 1—IMPORTANT PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS

Location of soils	Taxonomic classification	pH(1 : 2.5) Soil : Water	E.C. ds. m ⁻¹	C.E.C./ cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	Organic carbon g kg ⁻¹	Clay %	Exchangable metal, cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹			Dominant clay minerals
							Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	
Anandapur	Fine Loamy Ultic Haplustalf	5.62	0.18	10.9	4.30	24.8	3.90	0.70	0.13	Kaolinite
Bolpur	Fine Loamy Aeric Ochraqualf	5.96	0.07	17.7	4.50	54.8	9.50	4.70	0.21	Illite and kaolinite
Mohit- nagar	Coarse Loamy Aeric Haplaquept	6.02	0.17	23.7	19.2	24.8	3.36	0.24	0.14	Chlorite and inter- stratified minerals
Mondouri	Fine Loamy Aeric Fluvauquent	7.78	0.45	28.4	6.30	44.8	23.9	2.80	0.40	Montmor- illonite and illite

TABLE 2—KINETICS OF POTASSIUM ADSORPTION AND DESORPTION IN SOILS BY USING BATCH TECHNIQUE

Location of soils	K_a $\cdot 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	K_d 10^4 min^{-1}	K_{c-d}	ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹
Anandapur	4.05	33.9	0.12	5.27
Bolpur	4.59	1.52	3.67	-3.22
Mohitnagar	2.88	8.38	0.34	2.64
Mondouri	19.2	1.82	10.5	-5.83

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffractograms of Anandapur soil.

singular and that the hysteresis effect could be present¹⁵.

The values of the standard free energy change of K adsorption (ΔG°) are recorded in Table 2. In the present study, the overall selectivity of K⁺ against Ca²⁺ was best expressed by ΔG° values¹⁶ during desorption. The Bolpur and the

Mondouri soils exhibited negative ΔG° values indicating strong K preference of these soils. Goulding¹⁶ found strong potassium retention in soils that contained substantial quantities of 2 : 1 clay minerals (as in the case of Mondouri and the Bolpur soils). The positive ΔG° values for the Anandapur and the Mohitnagar soils implied that the driving force for the uptake of K⁺ ion onto the exchange complex was not favoured thermodynamically. The overall Ca²⁺ preference of the Mohitnagar soil may possibly be attributed to the organic phase of the soil. Strong binding of Ca²⁺ to organic matter has been noted by numerous authors^{17,18}. For the Anandapur soil, absence of specific sites for K⁺ could be the possible reason for positive ΔG° value.

The linear plots for potassium adsorption and desorption according to parabolic diffusion law (the corresponding r values ranging from 0.922 to 0.989; figures not shown) suggest that both adsorption and desorption in all the soils studied tended to conform to a diffusion-controlled mechanism^{2,5}. Further, the straight line relationships suggest that the intraparticle diffusion could be the rate-limiting process³. A better fit of the experimental data to the parabolic equation than the first order kinetic equation tends to further emphasise the importance of the diffusion-controlled exchange mechanism in the given K sorption/desorption processes.

Experimental

Four surface soil samples (0–15 cm) of contrasting properties were collected from different locations of West Bengal. The important physicochemical properties of the soils were probed by standard methodology¹⁹. In particular, the clay mineralogical make-up of the soils was obtained by X-ray diffraction of the Mg and K saturated clays²⁰.

The bulk of the kinetic studies with soils employed batch technique², which involved placing an exchanger and the absorbate in a reaction vessel such as a centrifuge tube. Each soil (3 g) and 50 ppm KCl solution (30 ml) were taken in several centrifuge tubes, followed by shaking different

tubes for different periods of time (5, 10, 30, 50, 60 and 120 min) at 25°; blanks were run simultaneously. The soil suspension was then centrifuged and the supernatant filtered (Whatman no. 42). The filtrate was analysed flame photometrically for K. The adsorption rate coefficient (K_a) was calculated from the graphical plot of $\log K$ vs t (Fig. 1) which yielded a straight line of slope $-K_a$ according to the first order kinetics of K-adsorption by the given soils. Here, K denotes the concentration of K^+ in the filtrate at time t^{21} .

For desorption studies, the residual soil from the adsorption run was re-suspended in 0.01 M $CaCl_2$ solution (30 ml), and shaken for the same time as that during the corresponding adsorption run. The contents of the tubes were then centrifuged and filtered. The filtrate was analysed for K by flame photometer. The desorption rate coefficient (K_d) of the first order desorption process was measured from the slope of the linear plot of $\log (K_0 - K_t)$ vs t (Fig. 2) where K_0 is the total amount of K^+ ion that could be released and K_t is the amount released at time t^{21} .

For a completely reversible reaction, the thermodynamic equilibrium constant (K_{eq}) for K-adsorption was obtained from the relation¹⁴, $K_{eq} = K_a/K_d$. The Gibbs standard free energy change (ΔG°) for the given exchange process was obtained from the equation¹⁴, $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{eq}$.

The K adsorption and desorption kinetic data were fitted to the parabolic diffusion equation by way of plotting percent K^+ , either adsorbed or desorbed, against square-root of time (t)²² in accordance with the requirements,

$$(K_t/K_0) = D_a t^{1/2}$$

where K_t is the quantity of K released at time t and K_0 is the amount released at equilibrium, while D_a is the apparent diffusion rate coefficient.

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